

Up to 270 ml of water are consumed per minute when using social media [1].

Social networks vary a lot, TikTok consumes about three times as much water as YouTube and Twitch [1].

Streaming 1 GB of data requires around 2 l of water in Germany, globally water requirements vary widely [2,3].

One hour of audio streaming per day requires approximately 50 l of water per year [2-4].

The water consumption for one hour of video streaming is around 6 l [2,3,5].

Streaming in HD (720p) reduces the amount of data by a factor of 10 compared to 4k [5].

Up to 150 MB of data is transferred per hour of mobile gaming, consuming around 300 ml of water [2,3,6].

The use of cloud storage requires around 180 ml of water per GB per year [7,8].

Sending an email or text message consumes around 0.15 ml of water [2,3,9].

A request (text/image) to a generative AI requires about 10-20ml of water [10].

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